

A quick note

Yesterday, you may have accidentally received a test version of our newsletter that was unfortunately sent out to the whole list because of a technical issue. We sincerely apologize for this! As you can see, we have been hard at work in creating a better version (html!) of our newsletter and have been smoothing out all the little details. So without further ado, we hope you enjoy this last newsletter of the year!

Introduction

Welcome to the last edition of the newsletter for this year! It has been a busy year, **and we are sorry to say goodbye to Erica**, who will **start a new job** next year. Luckily, she will still collaborate with us as **ambassador**. We wish you good luck with your **postdoc at Tilburg University!** Moreover, we are delighted to **welcome our new team member Stefano Giani**, a highly skilled Library Information Specialist from the University of Amsterdam! With fresh insights, he is ready to work on our ambitious agenda for next year.

The Diamond OA Expertise Centre Team ([Bregt](#), [Erica](#), [Juliana](#), [Femke](#), [Stefano](#), [Maria](#))

News and Resources

Poster 'Landscaping Diamond OA Journals' presented at CRAFT-OA Conference in Göttingen

The poster by **Chiara Livio** (project lead of Mapping and Monitoring Diamond OA) and **Erica** details different aspects of the process of compiling A curated list of Diamond OA journals in the Netherlands. **It describes the workflows and the challenges encountered**, the current status of the project, and the community engagement activities planned to bring the list to the relevant audiences that would benefit from it.

Ambassador's Letter to Young Academies in the Netherlands

Our **ambassadors** asked universities through their **young academies** to amend their **Recognition and Rewards (R&R)** policies to explicitly **value and protect researchers who work toward publishing reform** such as Diamond OA. Out of 14 Young Academies contacted, **six said they will change their policy** while three are still reluctant. We are considering organizing follow up activities for next year on this topic, so stay tuned! **Meanwhile, read the letter here: [Ambassadors' Letter to Young Academies in the Netherlands](#)**

Expertise Centre collaborates with European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH)

We are honored to be not only one of the advocates for the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH), but also one of the **eleven Diamond OA Capacity centers** established in Europe. **Ten more capacity centers are in the making. You can check all of them out here.** We are collaborating with EDCH by taking an active role in two of the task forces of the EDHC: Quality Alignment and Skills and Competences.

Survey for Diamond OA journal editors: collaboration Expertise Centre and OpenJournals

The Diamond OA Expertise Centre and [OpenJournals](#) are excited to announce a collaboration on a **survey for editors of Diamond OA journals**. It will address **editors** with queries about their **needs, wishes, and difficulties** when running a journal. We will send the survey **early 2026** to editorial boards of the Diamond OA journals that were identified Mapping and Monitoring project. **We will post the survey on our news channels as soon as its ready**, so watch this space!

In the Spotlight

- **Five Dutch journals** received **NWO funding to flip to Diamond Open Access**; read more [here](#).
- As part of our newly launched **Online Portfolio**, Erica interviewed **Hilde van Wijngaarden** on Making the Diamond Dream a Reality. Read the interview [here](#).
- The **Netherlands Open Access Books Community** launched on October 28, 2025 with Juliana participating in a **panel discussion**, and Bregt as moderator.
- We **presented** at the National Open Science Festival in Groningen on October 24, 2025.

Agenda

- February 2-6, 2026: [Global Summit Diamond Open Access](#). Bengaluru, IN
- February 5-6, 2026: [Towards New Horizons of Scholarly Publishing: National Meeting](#). Radboud University, Nijmegen
- February 25, 2026: [Open Divide Lecture: The Promise and Perils of Transparency and Openness](#). Online
- February 26-27, 2026: [Copim Conference: Exploring the Future of Community-Led Open Access Books](#). Loughborough, UK
- More events can be found on [our website](#) and on [EDHC site](#).

We welcome any feedback, ideas, or wishes to contribute that will enable us to further improve the newsletter (diamondexpertisecenter@gmail.com).

LinkedIn Website

Feel free to send the newsletter to your colleagues who are interested. They can sign up for the mailing list [here](#).

Deze e-mail is verstuurd aan [{{email}}](#). • Als je geen e-mails meer wilt ontvangen dan kun je je [hier afmelden](#). • Voeg erica.yu@eur.nl toe aan je adresboek voor een betere ontvangst.

